

Preparation and characterization of new donor-acceptor conjugated polymer derived from quinoline and carbazole

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Abstract : Quinoline and carbazole substituted oligo phenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) was synthesized from 2,6-dimethyl quinoline and 3,6-bis formyl-9-allylcarbazole through Wittig reaction. The synthesized conjugated oligomer was characterized by FT-IR and NMR and GPC chromatography. The oligomer shows excellent solubility in common organic solvents such as chloroform, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran and dimethylformamide. The weight average molecular weight of the oligomer is 3455. UV absorption (UV-Vis) and photoluminescence (PL) emission wavelengths of (QC-OPV) have a significant blue shift (410 and 450 nm) due to good electronic delocalization of the conjugated segments of the corresponding oligomer. The result indicates that QC-OPV has excellent optoelectronic properties.

Keywords : Donor-acceptor oligomer, quinoline, carbazole, Wittig route.

Introduction

Donor-acceptor conjugated polymers are promising materials for various application such as OLED, solar cell, PLEDs, semiconductors, etc.¹⁻³ because of their good organo solubility and tunable energy bands⁴. Quinoline based polymers are great interest because of having n-type conductivity upon doping and possessed excellent thermal stability⁵.

Carbazole based polymer have been previously synthesized by polycondensation and polymerization process because of their high photoconductive properties and electron donating characteristics. Therefore, these polymer showed interesting electrical, optical, photochemical properties⁶ extended glassy state with good thermal stability and moderately high oxidation potential due to carbazole conjugated system⁷.

Carbazole is a strong electron donating chromophore which is used as building blocks for new organic material⁸. For e.g. pyrido[4,3-*b*]carbazole and quinolino[4,3-*b*]carbazole alkaloids are naturally occurring important biologically active molecules and also studied the conductivity⁹. The present work deals with the synthesis of donor-acceptor conjugated polymer containing 2,6-dimethylquinoline and 9-allyl-9*H*-carbazole-3,6-dicarbaldehyde unit in their main chain via Wittig reac-

tion. The compounds were characterized by FT-IR, NMR, UV-Vis and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

The synthetic routes of the oligomer containing aromatic quinoline and carbazole are shown in Scheme 1. Monomer-1 was synthesized from carbazole and Vilsmier Hack reagent and after alkylated with allyl bromide¹⁰. Bromination of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) plays a key role during the synthesis of monomer-2. Initially, 2,6-bis(bromodimethyl)quinoline was synthesized from 2,6-dimethylquinoline. In this process NBS is used as a brominating and oxidizing agent and the bromination of quinoline was done by using benzoyl peroxide as an initiator.

2,6-Bis(bromomethylquinoline) was obtained as a yellow powder and directly converted into monomer-2 by treatment with triphenylphosphine in an overall yield of 76%. The structure of the phosphonium-ylide was confirmed by appearance of strong bands at 781 and 690 cm^{-1} (for C-P and P-Br stretching frequency) in IR spectra, multiplet formed at 7.3–7.7 ppm for aromatic hydrogens in NMR spectra. Methylene signal of 4.7 ppm shifted to 2.8 ppm (¹H NMR) indicates methylene group attached with phosphonium salt was confirmed.

Monomers (1 and 2) were confirmed by chromatographic and spectral technique. Final oligomer was pre-

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of quinoline substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV).

pared through Wittig reaction between phosphonium salt of quinoline and 9-allyl-9H-carbazole-3,6-dicarbaldehyde.

Characterization of quinoline substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) :

Quinoline and carbazole substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) was synthesized from monomer-1 and monomer-2 by using Wittig route and the synthetic procedure was sketched in Scheme 1. The final oligomer was well soluble in chloroform, dichloromethane, tetra-

hydrofuran and *N,N'*-dimethylformamide. Sodium methoxide was selected as an active base and used to deprotonate the phosphonium salt. Final oligomer QC-OPV was characterized by FTIR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy.

Fig. 1 shows the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the QC-OPV. The aromatic regions were found to be in three parts. Quinoline and phenylene nucleus was obtained in the range 7.69–7.52 ppm and the peak of trans-vinylene

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of QC-OPV.

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR (a) and ^{13}C NMR (b) spectra of QC-OPV.

was obtained at 7.44–7.48 ppm. In IR spectra, an absorption peak formed at around 983 cm^{-1} which confirmed the presence of trans-vinylene. From the ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy the peak was found in 129–136 ppm which showed the presence of phenylene and quinoline carbon regions and vinylene carbon formed at around 128 ppm. The average molecular weight was measured by GPC using polystyrene as the standard is 3455.

Optical characterization :

The optical properties and peak absorption wavelengths of the QC-OPV are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The UV-Vis and fluorescence absorption spectra of QC-OPV were

Fig. 3. UV-Vis absorption spectra of QC-OPV.

Fig. 4. PL absorption spectra of QC-OPV.

measured in various solvents such as DMF, THF, ethyl acetate, methanol and chloroform. The absorption spectra of QC-OPV exhibit three absorption bands at 260–300, 300–340 and 350–410 nm due to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ electronic transition. Quinoline and carbazole type conjugated oligomer shows a low energy broad band at 300–340 nm due to intramolecular charge transfer (CT) band and show almost identical maxima for both (UV-Vis and PL spectra) in the different solvents. The emission band was formed at around 360–450 nm with the same solvents. Fluorescence emission maximum shifted to longer wavelength when compared with the literature based on carbazole containing donor-acceptor conjugated polymer^{11,12}. This is mainly due to electronic character of substituents present in the carbazole moieties which is responsible for

the higher electron-donating character.

Experimental

Materials :

Carbazole, 2,6-dimethylquinoline, phosphorus oxy chloride, triphenylphosphine and NBS were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Mumbai, India. Benzoyl peroxide, chloroform, acetonitrile, methanol, acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide were purchased from SD Fine Chemicals, India.

Characterization methods :

FT-IR spectra were measured as KBr pellets with a midrange (500–4000 cm^{-1}) using a Thermo Nicolet 330 FTIR spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer using CDCl_3 as the solvent. UV-Vis spectra were carried out on a Shimadzu 1601 spectrophotometer and the photoluminescence spectra were taken on a (Hitachi F7000) fluorometer. The average molecular weight was measured from Perkin-Elmer series 200 model of gel permeation chromatography (GPC) system in THF solvents and calibrated with polystyrene standards.

Preparation of 9-allyl-9H-carbazole-3,6-dicarbaldehyde :

The 9-allyl-9H-carbazole-3,6-dicarbaldehyde was prepared as per the literature¹⁰.

Preparation of 2,6-bis(bromomethylquinoline) :

2,6-Dimethylquinoline (0.75 g) and benzoyl peroxide were dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) and benzene (2 : 1)¹³. The solution was refluxed for 18 h at 70 °C under nitrogen flow. Upon cooling, a part of the product precipitated along with succinimide. The precipitate was filtered off and washed with CCl_4 , to redissolve the product that had precipitated out. Two filtrates were combined and solvents were evaporated to obtain yellow solid wetted by red oil. The solid was washed with cold methanol to remove red oil and a light yellow solid was obtained. It was further washed with water and recrystallized in ethanol to obtain pure product. The yield was about 22%. ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.038 (9, 1H), 8.012 (10, 1H), 7.907 (11, 1H), 4.415 (13, 2H).

Preparation of 2,6-dimethyl(triphenylphosphonium-dibromo-methyl)quinoline :

In a 250 ml three necked round bottom flask, 2,6-bis

(bromomethylquinoline) and triphenylphosphine (1.2 g, 4.6 mmol) were dissolved with 20 ml of acetonitrile¹⁴. The solution was stirred overnight at 40 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The resulting brown precipitate was recrystallized from toluene-methanol mixture (2 : 1 ratio). The yield was about 76%. FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3045 (aromatic-CH), 1641 (aromatic C=N), 1471 (aromatic C=C), 758 (C-P), 694 (C-Br), 511 (P-Br); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 7.4–7.6 (30H, Ph_3P) 7.7 (3H, quinoline), 2.1 (CH_2).

Preparation of quinoline substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) :

To a stirred solution monomer-1 (0.064 g, 0.2 mmol) and monomer-2 (0.16 g, 0.2 mmol) in 15 ml of methanol and 5 ml of chloroform was added a solution of 51 mg of sodium methoxide in 10 ml of methanol at room temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was heated with stirring for 12 h. After 12 h the solution was filtered and 20 ml methanol was added in the filtrate solution and the solvent was removed to get green colour precipitate. Yield 68%; molecular weight 431; FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3049 (aromatic CH), 1892 (aromatic C=N), 1492 (aromatic C=C), 1600 (phenyl nucleus), 997 (trans-vinylene); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 7.55–7.57 (4H, m, 1,4-phenylene), 7.46–7.48 (4H, m, vinylene), 7.61–7.62 (3H, m, quinoline); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : 131.88 (phenyl carbons), 129.89 (vinylene carbons), 135.93, 156.17 (quinoline).

Conclusion

We have synthesized donor-acceptor oligomer consisting quinoline and carbazole type conjugated oligomer. The present oligomer is showing good solubility in common organic solvents and capable of exhibiting enhanced fluorescent properties. Quinoline substituted phenylene-vinylene oligomer was successfully synthesized through Wittig reaction using phosphonium salt of quinoline and 9-allyl-9H-carbazole-3,6-dicarbaldehyde without the formation of any side products. Quinoline substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) are blue photoluminescence materials and showing a strong photoemission in the blue region of the visible spectrum. Finally we conclude that quinoline substituted oligophenylene-vinylene (QC-OPV) is having fluorescence property in solution

state. This may be the important material in the field of optoelectronics.

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